

Home > News > CfA Bibliography for October 2014

Archives

Tags

- ASTRONOMICAL PLATES
- ASTRONOMY
- ASTRONOMY THESIS COLLECTION
- CFA BIBLIOGRAPHY
- CFA HISTORY
- CFA NEWS
- CULTURAL ASTRONOMY SERIES
- EVENTS
- HISTORY
- METADATA
- METASAT
- ORCID
- PHAEDRA
- UNIFIED ASTRONOMY THESAURUS
- VISUAL ASTRONOMY DISPLAY
- WOLBACH LIBRARY
- ZOONIVERSE

NEWS

CfA Bibliography for October 2014

Louise Rubin Updated on August 24, 2022

Refereed articles published by CfA authors in October 2014

[\(View this list in ADS 2.0 to filter, analyze, view, export, and sort\)](#)

WP NASA/ADS Query Importer error: this shortcode has been superseded by wp_nasaads_query_importer, see the documentation for its usage

Author Recent Posts

Louise Rubin

Boyden Observatory
through the 60"
Rockefeller Reflector

Visual Astronomy
Display: November 2014

